

Information (-ei/T) Method and Kaniadakis Entropy Part 2

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In a previous note (1), we argued that one may mimic Shannon's entropy for Tsallis entropy and argue that there exists a function $F(p) = -ei/T$ (information) such that d/dp (probability for an average $F(p)$) yields ei probability for an average. In the Tsallis case, probability used for an average is $p(ei)$ power q . The derivative acting on $p(ei)$ power q leaves $F(p) = -ei/T$, i.e. revealing the complete information associated with $-ei$, i.e. in d/dp Sum over i ei (Lagrange multiplier) $p(ei)$ power q . Thus, we argued that $p(ei)$ power q $dF/dp = 1$, because there is no further ei constraint. From this condition and $q=1$ yields $F(p) = \ln(p)$ one may obtain the Tsallis \ln_q . For Shannon's case, p $dF/dp = 1$, so there is a strong connection. This allowed us to find $F(p)$ from these various conditions.

In Part I, we considered this method for the Kaniadakis case and saw that p $dF/dp \neq 1$. We then suggested that $F(p)$ and p dF/dp (the two terms of d/dp (p F)) should be on equal footing, The first term is $-ei/T$, but the second cannot be equal to $-ei/T$, but is related, namely $-ei/T + 2p$ power $-k / (2k)$ which leads to somewhat of a problem.

In (2), a scaling differential equation is introduced: d/dp (p $B(p)$) = L $B(p/a)$ where L and a are constants. (2) shows that $\ln_k(p) = (p$ power $k - p$ power $-k) / (2k)$ is a solution, but that $(p$ power $k + p$ power $k) / 2 = l(p)$ is another. (2) then establishes a variational method to find Kaniadakis entropy by using: d/dp { Sum over i p $F(p) - p$ $l(p)$ } + b constraints } = 0. (We consider Sum over i ei $p(ei)$ as such a constraint.) Basically, we consider $B(p) = F(p)$ so that two terms of d/dp (p $F(p)$) yield a single term $F(p/a)$ where $F(p) = -ei/T$. This we argue is how one may have $F(p)$ and p dF/dp on the same footing, which we desired in Part I.

In (2), the explicit form of Kaniadakis entropy $S(k)$ is known a priori. As a second step, it is noted that $l(p)$ allows one to obtain the Kaniadakis distribution from a variational approach if one extremizes $S_k(p) - l(p)$.

What we wish to do is find the explicit form of $S(k,p) = -\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(ei) F(k,p(ei))$, i.e. find the explicit form of $F(p(ei))$ such that $F(k, p) = \ln(p)$ for $k=0$. There is already a Tsallis solution to this problem, but it uses p power q $dF/dp = 1$. We first suggest that there should be a reason for seeking a second power law solution such that $F(p,q) = -ei/T$ and limit $1-q=0$ $F(p,q) = \ln(p)$. We suggest that this reason may be a different probability for finding averages. In the Tsallis case, one uses $p(ei)$ power q , but usually (as in the Shannon case), $p(ei)$ is used. Thus, we seek an entropy of p $F(p)$.

We note that $F(p)$ and p dF/dp are the two terms of d/dp { p $F(p)$ }. Thus, the equivalence of terms so to speak seems to be that each satisfies the differential equation of (2) with the same L and a . We argue that the two terms of d/dp (p $F(p)$) are on the same footing as they are both solutions of the same differential equation. At the same time, the first term, $F(p) = -ei/T$ a priori.

Shannon and Tsallis Entropies

In both the Shannon and Tsallis cases: $F(p) = -ei/T$ ((1))

In the Shannon case: p $dF/dp = 1$ ((2a)) and in the Tsallis case: p power q $dF/dp = 1$ ((2b))

Here $p(e_i)$ is an unnormalized probability. As a result, we tried to argue in (1) that one may actually find a power law Tsallis distribution from the condition $p^q dF/dp = 1$ together with $q > 1$ yielding $F(p) = \ln(p)$. Furthermore, the presence of p^q in the Tsallis case is linked to the a priori constraint:

$$\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q \quad ((3))$$

We argued in (1), that for $d/dp (p^q F(p))$, the first term contains all of the information about $-e_i/T$ and the second term should be constant because there is no further e_i/T information to reveal. This leads to:

$$\ln q(p) = \{ p^{1-q} - 1 \} / (1-q) \quad ((4))$$

Kaniadakis Case

((4)) already shows that one may have a power law of p such that $F(p) = -e_i/T$, $p^q dF/dp = 1$ and $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} F(p) = \ln(p)$.

The Kaniadakis case is another power law scenario such that $F(p) = -e_i/T$ and $1-q = k = 0$ which begs the question: What is probability used for an average dF/dp ? In the Tsallis case, p^q is the a priori probability used to calculate a physical average, e.g.

$$\sum_i e_i p^q = E_{\text{total}} \quad ((5a))$$

Given that one has a second power law scenario which collapses to the Shannon case for $k=0$, one might suggest that the probability needed to calculate an average differs from p^q . In fact, in the Shannon case, the probability is $p(e_i)$, so one may postulate:

The Kaniadakis case is one for which: $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, $k > 0$ $F(p) = \ln(p)$ and $p(e_i)$ is used to calculate averages. ((5a))

This may provide justification for seeking a second power law result in addition to the Tsallis case.

One would then need to calculate, in a variational approach, or a link to an a priori constraint:

$$d/dp (p F(p)) \rightarrow e_i p(e_i) \quad ((6))$$

The first term $F(p)$ already yields this result, so as we argued in Part I, the second term $p dF/dp$ must yield an analogous result, i.e. both must be on the same footing. The problem, as seen in Part I, is that one cannot have:

$$p dF/dp = -e_i/T \quad ((7)) \text{ and satisfy other criteria.}$$

This then begs the question: How may one have $F(p)$ and pdF/dp be represented as being on the same footing? We suggest that a scaling differential equation introduced in (2) allows for this.

Scaling Differential Equation from (2)

(2) introduces the scaling differential equation:

$$d/dp \{ p B(p) \} = L B(p/a) \quad ((7))$$

(2) notes that $B(p) = \ln k(p) = 1/2k (p \text{ power } k - p \text{ power } -k)$ and $u(p) = 1/2 (p \text{ power } k + p \text{ power } -k)$ are both solutions with:

$$L = \sqrt{1-k^2} \text{ and } a = \{ (1-k)/(1+k) \} \text{ power } 1/(2k) \quad ((8)) \text{ in both cases.}$$

Without knowing explicit solutions of ((7)) one may consider the following.

If one sets $B(p) = F(p)$, then ((7)) is minus the variation of the Kaniadakis entropy and yields $L F(p/a)$, but there is still the condition that $F(p) = -ei/T$. If the constraint is $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ Lagrange multiplier, then ((7)) seems to be consistent with a variational approach.

In other words, ((7)) is a way to deal with the two terms of $d/dp (p F(p))$ together to create a single term linked with a single constraint, i.e. $e_i p(e_i)$. ((7)) appears to be the reason for having the two terms of $d/dp (p F(p))$ rest on the same footing - they are both solutions of ((7)) and so carry the same information so to speak.

(2) goes on to define $\sum_i p(e_i) u(p(e_i)) = I_v$ and argues for extremizing:

$$S(\text{Kaniadakis}) - I_v + b \text{ constraints}, \text{ where } b \text{ represents Lagrange multiplier(s)} \quad ((9))$$

but it seems that it is the scaling differential ((7)) with identification of $B(p)$ as $F(p)$ which automatically shows that one can have two terms essentially yield one with all the information $-ei/T$ for the case of $\sum_i e_i p(i)$ as the a priori constraint.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Shannon's approach has: $\ln(p(e_i)) = -ei/T$ for $p(e_i)$ unnormalized and $p d \ln(p)/dp = 1$. It is possible to introduce a power law function, $F(p,q) = -ei/T$, where $1-q$ is a power of p such that $q=1$ yields $\ln(p)$. If one also wishes to have: probability used for averages $dF/dp = 1$, then for probability used for averages $= p \text{ power } q$, one obtains the Tsallis result, $\ln_q(p) = \{ p \text{ power } (1-q) - 1 \} / (1-q)$. This begs the question: Why would there be another power law $\ln k(p)$ function? If $\ln k(p) = -ei/T$ and $k \rightarrow 0 \ln k(p) = \ln(p)$, what would be the motivation? We suggest that a different probability for averaging could be the motivation. In other words, instead of using p

power q , one could use the usual $p(e_i)$. This could be based on physical reasons for averaging with $p(e_i)$ power q versus $p(e_i)$.

One would then require that $d/dp (p F(p))$ be linked with the only $-e_i/T$ information, namely that in $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$. The first term is $F(p) = -e_i/T$, so we argued in Part I that the second term is not 1 (as in the Tsallis case), but is on the same footing. In Part I, we saw that it cannot be $-e_i/T$, but rather is $-e_i/T + f(p)$, which does not make it appear on the same footing. In (2), however, a scaling differential equation is provided: $d/dp (p B(p)) = L B(p/a)$, where L and a are constants. If $B(p) = F(p)$, the problem is solved as two terms map into the single $F(p) = -e_i/T$ type of term $L B(p/a)$. One may see that in the Kaniadakis situation, this is the case.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Tsallis Entropy from Maximization of Entropy and the Condition of Stability part 3 (preprint, zenodo, 2025)
2. Scarfone, A. and Wada, T. Multi-Additivity in Kaniadakis Entropy (2024)
<https://www.mdpi.com/1099-4300/26/1/77>